

Protein Carbonyl Group Assay Kit Instruction

I. Significance of Measurement

This assay kit is designed for the detection of carbonyl group in proteins. The kit can easily detect the amount of carbonyl groups within tissues, serum, cultured cells and organelle samples with high sensitivity. The detection with no expensive apparatus involved has a simple method for pretreatment and can be applied widely for the diagnosis of diseases like rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, diabetes and Parkinson's disease and for the assessment of health food and drugs for antioxidant purpose and cosmetics. Also the kit can be used for the judgment of organism damage caused by environmental factors like radiation or chemical toxins.

II. Reagent Compositions and Preparation

1. 100 T/ 48 Samples

Reagent I: Homogenate Medium. Liquid without color. 1 Bottle×100ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent II: Light Yellow Liquid. 1 Bottle×5ml. Preserved at 4°C in darkness.

Reagent III: Yellow Liquid. 1 Bottle×20 ml. Preserved at 4°C in darkness.

Reagent IV: Colorless Liquid. 1 Bottle×20 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent V: Colorless Liquid. 1 Bottle×60 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent VI: Colorless Liquid. 2 Bottles×70 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagents Required: Absolute Ethanol (Analytical Grade). Ethyl Acetate (Analytical Grade).

Preparation of ethyl acetate ethanol solution: Mix both chemicals with the same volume right before use.

2. 50T/ 24 Samples

Reagent I: Homogenate Medium. Liquid without color. 1 Bottle×50ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent II: Light Yellow Liquid. 1 Bottle×2.5ml. Preserved at 4°C without light struck.

Reagent III: Yellow Liquid. 1 Bottle×10 ml. Preserved at 4°C without light struck.

Reagent IV: Colorless Liquid. 1 Bottle×10 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent V: Colorless Liquid. 1 Bottle×30 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Reagent VI: Colorless Liquid. 1 Bottle×70 ml. Preserved at 4°C.

Chemicals Required: Absolute Ethanol (Analytical Grade). Ethyl Acetate (EA) (Analytical Grade).

Preparation of ethyl acetate ethanol solution: Mix both chemicals with the same volume right before use.

III. Procedures

1. Serum or Plasma Samples

- Pretreatment: Serum and plasma can be detected directly
- Total Protein Determination: Biuret assay with kit available.
- Procedures

Compositions (ml)	Sample	Comparison
Sample	0.1	0.1
Reagent III	0.4	
Reagent IV		0.4
Vortex for 1min for blending purpose and warm the solution in a water bath at 37°C for 30 min without light struck. (Step I)		
Reagent V	0.5	0.5
Vortex for 1 min and at 4°C, centrifuge the mixture at 12,000 rpm for 10 min and discard the supernatant (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
Reagent VI	1.25	1.25
Mix thoroughly and warm the solution in a water bath at 37°C for 15 min.		

Vortex to fully dissolve the pellets. Centrifuge the solution at 12,000 rpm for 15 min. Zero the cuvettes with 0.5 cm path length at 370 nm with reagent VI. Extract the supernatant and record the optical density (OD) absorbed at 370 nm.

- Formula

$$D_{\text{carotenyl}} \text{ nmol/mg} = \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{comparison}}}{22 \times \frac{\text{Path Length}}{0.5 \text{ cm}}} \times 125 \times 10^3 + C_{\text{protein}} \text{ mg/L}$$

- Example

Human serum 0.1 ml was measured and the OD values were 0.006 and 0.036 respectively. Also, the protein concentration was 54.30 mg/ml.

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{carotenyl}} \text{ nmol/mg} &= \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{comparison}}}{22 \times \frac{\text{Path Length}}{0.5 \text{ cm}}} \times 125 \times 10^3 + C_{\text{protein}} \text{ mg/L} \\ &= \frac{0.036 - 0.006}{22 \times 0.5} \times 125 \times 10^3 + (54.3 + 1000) = 0.628 \text{ nmol/mg} \end{aligned}$$

2. Tissue Samples

a. Tissue Homogenization

Weigh the tissue precisely and add reagent I with the ratio of 1 g tissue to 9 ml reagent I. Homogenize the mixture in an ice water bath and centrifuge at 2,500 rpm for 10 min. Extract the supernatant.

b. Extract 0.45 ml supernatant and add 0.05 ml reagent II. Set aside the mixture at RT for 10 min. and centrifuge the mixture at 11,000 rpm for 10 min. Extract supernatant for carbonyl group and protein concentration measurement.

c. Procedures

Compositions (ml)	Sample	Comparison
Pre-treated Sample	0.1	0.1
Reagent III	0.4	
Reagent IV		0.4
Vortex for 1min for blending purpose and warm the solution in a water bath at 37°C for 30 min without light struck. (Step I)		
Reagent V	0.5	0.5
Vortex for 1 min and at 4°C, centrifuge the mixture at 12,000 rpm for 10 min and discard the supernatant (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
EA/Ethanol Solution	1.0	1.0
Repeat the previous step (Step II).		
Reagent VI	1.25	1.25
Mix thoroughly and warm the solution in a water bath at 37°C for 15 min.		

Vortex to fully dissolve the pellets. Centrifuge the solution at 12,000 rpm for 15 min. Zero the cuvettes with 0.5 cm path length at 370 nm with reagent VI. Extract the supernatant and record the optical density (OD) absorbed at 370 nm.

d. Formula

$$b_{\text{carbonyl}} \text{ nmol/mg} = \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{comparison}}}{22 \times \frac{\text{Path Length}}{0.5 \text{ cm}}} \times 125 \times 10^3 + \frac{C_{\text{protein}}}{\text{mg/L}}$$

e. Example

10% rat lung tissue homogenate was prepared and measured with OD values equal to 0.026 and 0.012 respectively. The protein concentration was 6.520 mg/ml.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{b}_{\text{Carbonyl}} \text{ nmol/mg} &= \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{Sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{Comparison}}}{22 \times \frac{\text{Path Length}}{0.5 \text{ cm}}} \times 125 \times 10^5 + \frac{C_{\text{Protein}}}{\text{mg/L}} \\ &= \frac{0.026 - 0.012}{22 \times 0.5} \times 125 \times 10^5 + (6.52 + 1000) = 2.440 \text{ nmol/mg} \end{aligned}$$

IV. Notes

1. While washing the pellets with EA ethanol solution, the vortex should be violent with the period no less than 1 min. The desirable pellets should be white and the pellets can be washed for more times under the circumstance of yellow pellets remaining. Otherwise the results will be higher than the actual ones.
2. The velocity of centrifugation should not be lowered or otherwise the results will increase.
3. It is recommended to use the round-bottom flask so that the pellets can be fully contacted with the EA ethanol mixture.